

Sustainable development of economies based on the tool of the digital socio-economic model and measures to counter COVID-19

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Аннотация. На сегодняшний день уже имеются предпосылки для оптимизации мер по противодействию COVID-19 как в отдельных регионах, странах, так и в глобальном контексте. Речь идет о статистике известных моделей эпидемии. Цель статьи – обосновать возможность оптимизации мер противодействия пандемии COVID-19 на основе использования инструментов цифровой социально-экономической модели. Дальнейшее развитие цифровой социально-экономической модели осуществлялось путем стандартизации 5-балльного Индекса самоизоляции Яндекса и построения его мультилогистической аппроксимации. Модельные графики распространения пандемии были получены путем модификации мультилогистического приближения. Они подтверждают адекватность разработанной авторами цифровой социально-экономической модели. Данная модель может быть использована для оптимизации мер по противодействию COVID-19 для поддержки приемлемого роста экономик отдельных стран и регионов, их устойчивого социально-экономического развития.

Abstract. These days, there are already prerequisites for optimizing measures to counter COVID-19 both in individual regions, countries, and in a global context. It is spoken of the statistics of known epidemic models. The purpose of the article is to substantiate the possibility of optimizing measures to counter the COVID-19 pandemic based on the use of tools of the digital socio-economic model. The further development of the digital socio-economic model was carried out by standardizing the 5-point score Yandex self-isolation Index and its multilogistic approximation building. The model graphs of the spread of the pandemic were obtained by modifying the multilogistic approximation. They confirm the adequacy of the digital socio-economic model developed by the authors. This model can be used to optimize measures to counter COVID-19 to support the acceptable growth of the economies of individual countries and regions, their sustainable socio-economic development.

Ключевые слова: устойчивое развитие, цифровая социально-экономическая модель, COVID-19.

Keywords: sustainable development, digital socio-economic model, COVID-19.

Introduction

1.1. Problem description

In defiance of all expectations the coronavirus disease (COVID-19) would lead to a global pandemic, numerous lockdowns, and global economic crisis.

COVID-19 has spread throughout the world in a very short time and affected, in varying degrees, the socio-economic development worldwide. It is too early to talk about overcoming or localizing the development of the COVID-19 pandemic. Different countries of the world are being hit by the next waves of growth the number of new infected and the coronavirus mutations with frightening constancy. Each subsequent wave turns out to be much more dangerous than the previous one, and the rate of viral spread is skyrocketing. Under the influence of the pandemic, each country suffers human and economic losses and is forced to look for new lines of approach and solutions in order to maintain the sustainability of its socio-economic development.

Each wave of COVID-19 is accompanied by increasingly rising death rates. Therefore, the human losses in the United States amounted to more than 638,711 people at the end of August, 2021. This exceeds the losses of the United States in eve-

ry war in which it took part. In Russia, over the same period, the COVID-19 deaths were 179,233 people [9]. Johns Hopkins University [8] has shown that more than 4.5 million people have already died worldwide. According to various estimates, the world will lose about 10-12 million more people before the end of the pandemic.

Economic losses from COVID-19 are formed due to direct and indirect losses: 1) premature death, temporary or complete disability, health deterioration; 2) lockdowns and other restrictions, a decrease in business activity due to the obvious economic uncertainty. All this have a negative impact on the socio-economic development of each country. Death loss is understood as GDP that was not received due to the premature death of one person because of the coronavirus. The United States suffers the largest economic losses from the COVID-19 pandemic - \$50.3 billion. Brazil and France became the other two of the top three hardest hit countries. Their losses amounted to \$28.6 billion and \$15 billion. Russia's economic losses amounted to \$4.2 billion [17]. Globally, direct economic losses have already exceeded \$10 trillion.

As the number of regions of the Earth experiencing problems with climate, ecology, demogra-

phy, the emergence of superinfections increases, it can be assumed that the COVID-19 epidemics will recur. Studies of all aspects of the COVID-19 pandemic are relevant to increase the sustainability of the socio-economic development of individual regions and countries. The development of digital models to optimize measures to counter the current epidemic and possible epidemics in the future is of the utmost interest from the point of view of economic sustainability.

The databases [8, 9, 18] on a variety of contacts between sick and healthy should be used in known epidemic models. The indicator of the number of contacts is decisive for modeling optimal epidemic control measures, and it is also necessary for the formation of sustainable socio-economic development pathway of territorial entities, regions and countries. Let us take a closer look at this.

1.2. Case study

Russian economist Grachev, I.D., proposed a comprehensive digital model of economic optimal anti-epidemic measures in his work [12]. It combines models of anti-epidemic measures management and models of economic growth management. A slightly modified SIR model was used as a basic model of anti-epidemic measures management. A probabilistic model of mixed economic systems developed by the author was used as a model of economic growth. These models have been combined into a single system of discretized equations, studied, visualized and proven to be accurate. For the model, the data were selected for Moscow and Russia at the beginning of 2020.

In subsequent works Grachev, I.D. [13, 14, 15], assessed the economic results of various quarantine options using a combined digital economic-epidemic model. On its basis, the economic consequences of the implementation of the basic version of containment measures in the regions of Russia were determined, and their scientific analysis was carried out. The initial conditions for the calculations were the dynamics of the daily increase in COVID-19 infected from April 1 to April 8, 2020. Three versions for containment measures were considered and the likelihood of their development was substantiated. The proposed model can be used to select containment measures and assess the possible economic consequences for each region of Russia.

Researchers Acemoglu, D., Chernozhukov, V., Werning, I. and Whinston, M.D., developed the Multi-Risk SIR (MR-SIR) model [1]. The model took into account age differences in infection, hospitalization and mortality rates between homogeneous groups using the example of the United States. The authors determined that the model that combines measures to reduce interaction between groups and increase isolation of infected individuals will lead to reduction in economic losses and mortality.

The spread patterns of COVID-19 reviewed by Avery, C., Bossert, W., Clark, A., Ellison, G., and Ellison, S.F. [4]. It was noted that there are two main approaches to modeling the spread of COVID-19: "Mechanistic" and "Phenomenological". The distinction between these approaches is likewise in many ways to the distinction between structural models and behavioural theory of firms in the economy. However, mechanistic models take into account the basic processes of the spread of the pandemic and therefore are more effective. Mechanistic models

can be viewed as analogous to macroeconomic models.

SIR (Susceptible / Infectious / Recovered) is the most common model for investigating the spread of COVID-19. The SIR model is similar to the continuous-time Markov chain model, where only a limited number of state transitions are possible. Individuals in the SIR model are considered infinitely divisible. All transitions between states are modeled as exponential processes that can be characterized by a half-life. Time delays can be included in the model. For example, the presence of incubation period for SARS-CoV-2 of 5-6 days permits to expand the SIR model to SEIR and include the fourth state ("Exposed") in it. The SAIR model includes an additional "asymptomatic" infected condition ("compartmental model").

Several variants of the SIR model allow for biological parameters: modeling of disease transmission depending on the frequency and density of contacts; geographic data and demographic structures; record of reproduction and mortality; loss of immunity, etc. An increase in parameters leads to difficulties in comparing model predictions if they describe fundamentally different processes or different kinds of people. It presents 30 open source SIR-like models available for modeling and parameterization.

The most important and difficult thing in modeling is the heterogeneity of the behavior of individuals and its change over time. Obviously, the spread of COVID-19 will be accompanied by "safe amount of distance". This will result in reduction of the differences between mechanistic and phenomenological models.

There are three more problems in forecasting using SIR models: 1) nonlinearity, 2) dynamics, 3) lag in the start of the introduction of epidemic control measure. The diagnostic tools of the classical model cannot be used to obtain good extrapolations of the model (many models can be used in the early stages of the pandemic with an exponential increase in the number of infected, and only some models can determine the peak of infection, after which the number of new infections begins to decline).

Scientists Brotherhood, L., Kircher, P., Santos, C., and Tertilt, M., undertook a study of the role of test and age composition in the pandemic [6]. Regular tests reduce uncertainty. The age heterogeneity of the population pushes young people not to take epidemic control measures seriously, because they are less likely to die than the elderly. The standard SIR epidemic model was supplemented with the time parameter of an individual's stay at work and outdoors. An increase in these parameters bring a higher risk of infection.

Professor John H. Cochrane noted in his blog on May 4, 2020, that using the classical SIR model to predict the spread of Covid-19 could be misleading [7]. This followed from the assumption of the constant rate accounting of infection during human contact. The standard SIR model uses a constant (the assumption of an exponential infection growth). Its consequence is a time-limited further increase in infections due to a decrease in the number of susceptible people in the population. However, the virus is not transmitted from sick people to recovered. It is necessary to reduce the frequency of contacts before the transition to herd immunity at individual cities, regions and countries level. In order

to take these features into account Chad Jones and Jesús Fernández-Villaverde added three lags to the standard SIR model: D – dead, C – convalesce and immune, N – number of population. This enabled the model to use exponential decay rather than a fixed lag to determine time. This model proved more effective.

Jeremy Greenwood, Philipp Kircher, Cezar Santos and Michèle Tertilt undertook a study on the impact of sexual encounter on the spread of the Covid-19 pandemic using the example of Malawi, Africa [16]. They found that 12% of Malawi's population is infected with HIV, 18% of all sexual contacts are casual, and contraception is used in 33% of cases. A theoretical general equilibrium search model was built to analyze the spread of Covid-19 in Malawi. It took into account the patterns for selecting people with knowledge of the possibility of infection. The model, calibrated by the researchers, can be used to study the impact of possible options for limiting sexual encounter on the effectiveness of measures to counter the COVID-19 pandemic. It was revealed that it depends on the behavioral changes of individuals and the effects of equilibrium. The pattern obtained by the authors complements the epidemiological research findings.

Bognanni, M., Hanley, D., Kolliner, D., Mitman, K., found that the effectiveness of measures to combat epidemics requires an integrated economic and epidemiological approach [5]. They developed a spatial micro level model with economic and epidemiological variables. An empirical assessment of the model was carried out the relationship between health status, mobility, employment, and non-pharmaceutical interventions with the daily update of coronavirus infections for individual US counties. If there is no medical intervention, the model predicts an initial period of exponential growth in new cases of infection, followed by a long period of illness and slowdown in economic growth. The simulation results concluded that the number of infected can sharply decrease during vaccination campaign in regions and cities and keep the dynamics of infections at a low level for 2 years.

Acemoglu, D., Makhdoumi, A., Malekian, A., and Ozdaglar, A., studied the impact of testing on voluntary safe amount of distance in disseminating the spread of Covid-19 [2]. The researchers found that the effect of testing on infections is non-monotonic. This means that even the most optimal testing policy will not fully exploit the potential to counter the spread of Covid-19.

Farboodi, M., Jarosch, G., and Shimer, R., investigated a quantitative approach to studying voluntary restraints on beneficial social activity in order to reduce internal and external health risks during the spread of Covid-19 [11]. They calibrated the model for external factors, compared the obtained forecasts with the real-time data on social activity and mortality. It has been proven, according to the United States, that sufficiently sustained safe amount of distance leads to a decrease in the spread of Covid-19. The expected economic losses from the COVID-19 pandemic in the United States are estimated at \$12,700 per person with a hands off balance and \$8,100 per person with an optimal policy. This optimal policy generates such large welfare gains as a result of shifting costs away from fatalities and towards sustained social distancing.

Fang, H., Wang, L., and Yang, Y., Chinese researchers, quantified the causal effect of mobility limitations (data from Wuhan since January 23, 2020) on coronavirus containment (2019-nCoV) [10]. The results showed that the isolation reduced inflows to Wuhan by 76.64%, outflows from this city by 56.35% and intra-city movements by 54.15%. The simulation study has shown that the isolation of Wuhan since January 23, 2020, has significantly reduced the total number of infections outside Wuhan. COVID-19 infections would be 64.81% higher in 347 Chinese cities outside Hubei Province and 52.64% higher in another 16 cities in Hubei Province in the absence of city isolation.

Alvarez, F.E., Argente, D., and Lippi, F. [3] investigated the impact of controlling pandemic deaths on getting out of isolation while minimizing economic costs. To that end, the epidemiological SIR model and the linear formalization of the problem of dynamic control of the economy were used. The optimal policy depends on the proportion of the infected and vulnerable in the population. The SIR model was parameterized based on COVID-19 data and an economic assessment of lockdown losses. The quantitative estimates of the intensity and duration of the optimal isolation policy are obtained. Lack of testing increases economic losses and shortens the duration of optimal isolation. When lockdown and testing are optimal, they are equivalent to a simultaneous 2% drop in GDP.

According to the results of scientists, inference should be drawn that the most promising option for modeling the COVID-19 development and creating COVID-19 medical countermeasures can be the modified SIR model with certain parameters or the combination of the SIR model with economic models, in particular with a probabilistic mixed economies model. This approach makes it possible to take into account the epidemic and economic factors of the development of the pandemic. The data obtained can be used to establish the conditions for increasing the socio-economic development of individual regions and countries. Let us take a closer look at this.

Materials and Methods

The case of Taiwan shows that the task of counter-proliferation of COVID-19 is solvable. The organization of epidemic control measures has preserved an acceptable economic growth of 2-3% with the number of patients less than 1000 people and 7 deaths in 2020. Therefore, economic growth in Russia could be sustained with less than 70 deaths in 2020 with optimal epidemic management. However, neither Russia nor the world at large was able to effectively use government (The Ministry of Health, The Ministry of Economic Development, etc.) digital information data on countering COVID-19. The article will substantiate the possibility of optimizing the management of epidemic control measures, provided that an acceptable economic growth is maintained.

The first digital socio-economic model for managing COVID-19 countermeasures was proposed by the authors in April, 2020 [12, 13]. It was based on the classical SIR model with the parameters of the results of the pre-lockdown development of the epidemic in China and Europe and the probabilistic model of mixed economies developed by Grachev, I.D. The model takes into account the dependence of the daily growth of the

average number of contacts per person per day (β) and the cost per patient (z):

$$\frac{dS(t)}{dt} = -\beta \times \frac{S(t) \times I(t)}{N} \quad (1)$$

$$\frac{dI(t)}{dt} = +\beta \times \frac{S(t) \times I(t)}{N} - \gamma \times I(t) \quad (2)$$

$$\frac{dR(t)}{dt} = +\gamma \times I(t) \quad (3)$$

$$a_{i+1} = a_i + \alpha(\beta) \times a_i - \alpha_0 \times a_i - z \times I(i) \quad (4)$$

$S(t)$ – Individuals prone to disease;

$S(0) = N \approx 50 \times 10^6$.

When carrying out the first experimental calculations, N equals 50×10^6 , which corresponds to 30% of the Russian population, taking into account the potential immunity of a part of the population and distributed living over a very large territory.

$I(t)$ – Individuals, infected and capable of transmitting infection;

$R(t)$ – Individuals, "retired" after recovery or death;

β – Indicator, proportional to the average number of contacts per person per day;

$\gamma = 1/t$ – Inversely proportional to the average time of infection by an infected individual;

a_i – Indicator, interpreted the country's GDP;

α_0 – Inevitable amortization of GDP;

$\alpha_0 < \alpha$ – Growth indicator.

z – Costs per patient per day (from 10 to 100 thousand rubles).

Since the effectiveness of all known antiviral drugs is poor, it is only through a single control parameter (the intensity of human contacts) that the model and optimization of the life of society can be influenced.

Taking into account the refined parameters of the SIR model and control parameters ($\approx 10,000$ cases at the height of the epidemic), it can be argued that there was a decrease in contacts by half during the first month before mass immunization for the socio-economic optimum, followed by maintaining contacts at a level of 0.7 from the reference value. Integral suppression of contacts to a level of 0.7 from the reference one is possible almost without suppression of labor contacts in the main areas of production activity and provision of services through retail, leisure, transport [19].

The proposed model [12, 15] was valid until August, 2020. This was due to the fact that actual contacts exceeded the nominal level during the holiday season.

Figure 1 shows an adjustment of the model for Moscow with enhanced disclosure of data on the 175th day since the pandemic began. The level of coincidence of actual and model data is more than adequate for socio-economic consequence assessment and for optimal management of the integral frequency of contacts.

Fig. 1. The results of adjusting the model for Moscow, provided that contacts are disclosure on the 175th day since the pandemic began
Source: prepared by the authors.

Data of contacts [8, 9, 17, 18, 19], structured by economic sectors, is sufficient to accurately distribute anti-epidemic constraints at the industry level, while minimizing the suppression of labor contacts. However, this data does not contain information on the share of contacts distribution by industry.

In general, the digital socio-economic model with a certain choice of parameters in the equations (1)-(4) showed good approximation of the real and model results, as well as economic results at the end of the epidemic year. The authors are not aware of the models that presented the best results for actual patients, despite the use of much more complex equations and artificial intelligence.

This equates to consider the authors' hypothesis about the dominant impact on the result of accidental infections and the management of epidemic control measure (the parameter $\beta(t)$) correct.

Consequently, this equates to abandon the complications of the fundamental equations (1)-(4) and focus on digital modeling of the parametric control $\beta(t)$, since the authors are not able to influence the random clustering criterion of infections.

In previous works [12, 13, 14, 15], the authors estimated the parameter $\beta(t)$ for the future

from general considerations about the reflexive nature of the control response growth and decline in the number of actual patients, as well as the possibility of its multilogistic performance.

To date, the authors have massive qualitative estimates of the parameters of the intensity of contacts, which makes it possible to assess the validity of the approximations made [8, 9, 17, 18, 19].

All further equations are established for Moscow, since this corresponds more closely to the equations (1)-(3) than for the whole of Russia. In addition, the authors refined some estimates of the model parameters, which were carried out either on the basis of the most primary data on the epidemic in China (March 2020), or intuitively.

In particular, it was assumed that 1/3 of the population would not be infected as a matter of experience of previous epidemics. These days, a number of officials make the same estimations about Russia. Therefore, we have every reason to preserve it.

The model also assumes that the date of appearance of the first infected person is unknown, and that in fact only 50% of the actually diseased people are recorded. It is currently known that the registration rate varied over time from the beginning of the epidemic to the date of this study.

In the work, the authors assumed a linear efficiency gains in the registration of infected people from 40% to 80%, with the possibility of varying it, since it is hard to obtain accurate data. The rest of the parameters correspond to those adopted in the works [12, 13, 14, 15].

In order to use the Yandex self-isolation Index $Ya(t)$ to assess the impact of epidemic control measure on the $\beta(t)$, the standardization was carried out according to the equation (5):

$$\beta(t) = \beta(0) \times (4.5 - Ya(t)) / 4.5 \quad (5)$$

$Ya(t)$ – Standardized Yandex self-isolation Index for Moscow.

Results and discussion

Figure 2 shows the result of the standardization and its “edged” representation of the multilogistic curve. The a priori choice of a multilogistic approximation to the standardized by the $\beta(t)$ Yandex self-isolation Index causes problems due to the sawtooth qualitative contact changes on weekends and holidays. The general character of the curve is retained with any choice of edging or averaging.

Figures 3 and 4 show the comparative curves of the dynamics of the observed and model actual patient census in Moscow for the $\beta(t)$, varying according to the standardized Yandex Index (Ya) and its multilogistic approximation, respectively.

Fig. 2. Multilogistic approximation of the Yandex Index (Ya)
Source: prepared by the authors

Fig. 3. The observed and model patient census according to the standardized Yandex Index (Ya)
Source: prepared by the authors

Fig. 4. The observed and model patient census according to the multilogistic approximation
Source: prepared by the authors

Taking into account the level of stochasticity of the observed infections inherent in the model, the model curves have no significant distinctions between themselves, with the exception of the “saw” of weekends typical for the $Ya(t)$ -model. Keep in mind that the actually observed patient census has no such a clear weekend effects. Therefore, they can be ignored.

However, there is an apparent identical difference of both model curves with the actually observed one in terms of the distance between the extremum of the first and second waves, which cannot be eliminated by any reasonable standardization of the Yandex Index. It can be assumed that the internal structure of contacts changes when leaving the regular working hours during the holiday

season; however, it is not possible to effectively test this hypothesis in one season.

In the economic part of the model, which is essential for the optimization of containment measures, a small shift in the extremum of the second wave is not of fundamental importance.

In general, this part of the modeling shows that the standardization of the Yandex self-isolation Index and its multilogistic approximation give a sense of fully reflecting reality. This confirms the

hypothesis about the feasibility of multilogistic approximations for the parameter $\beta(t)$.

Let us show that, it is possible to obtain model curve graphics that are no different from real ones within the framework of small modifications of the multilogistic approximation. Figure 5 shows a multilogistic curve graph with a shifted second contact flattening of the curve compared to the primary $Y_a(t)$.

Fig. 5. Multilogistics with a shift
Source: prepared by the authors

Figure 6 shows a comparison of the observed and model patient census with the values of the parameter $\beta(t)$ in accordance with Figure 5. The obtained match can be considered knowingly satisfactory for socio-economic evaluations. Herewith, it should be noted that the disparity in the fall in patient census after extrema requires additional study.

Figure 7 shows the dependence of the economic recession for Moscow on the intensity of sup-

pression of the second wave (the range of 0-400 corresponds to the values of the parameter $\beta(t)$ over the 0.6 to 0.8 range during the second wave). The most significant in this part of the simulation is the possibility of optimizing the background suppression of contacts at this stage, albeit with a noticeably lower economic impact.

Fig. 6. The observed and model patient census
Source: prepared by the authors

Fig. 7. The dependence of the decay on the suppression of the second wave
Source: prepared by the authors

Substitution the calculated observed patient census $y(t)$ with a multilogistic approximation of the parameter $\beta(t)$ (Fig. 6) for the actually observed patient census does not lead to significant changes in the estimated economic decline. This is reflected in Figure 8.

Conclusion

The results obtained in the course of the research made it possible to draw the following inferences.

1. The expected direct economic losses from the COVID-19 pandemic on a global scale will be about \$10-12 trillion. The economic losses of each

country depend on their development. Obviously, these losses will have a negative impact on socio-economic development. First of all, they will affect the growth of the unevenness of all components of

the current industrial relations system, the negative dynamics of the consumer market, the emergence of new systemic risks in the development of the business environment.

Fig. 8. The dependence of the decay on the suppression of the second wave with a multilogistic approximation
Source: prepared by the authors

2. To counter the negative impact of the COVID-19 pandemic and to conduct a more detailed study of the current socio-economic and epidemic situation, it is necessary to develop new digital models. The use of these models will help to optimize the management of epidemic control measures and possible epidemics in the future, to develop new approaches to increase the socio-economic resilience of individual regions and countries.

3. The first digital socio-economic model for managing epidemic control measures proposed by the authors is based on combining the classical SIR model with data from the pre-quarantine development of the epidemic in China and Europe and the probabilistic model of mixed economies, developed by Professor Grachev, I.D. The actual data and the data calculated by the model from April to August, 2020, practically coincided; therefore, the developed model can be used to assess the socio-economic consequences and optimal management of the integral frequency of contacts.

4. In the course of the further development of the digital socio-economic model, the standardization of the 5-point Yandex self-isolation Index and its multilogistic approximation were carried out. This confirmed the hypothesis for the permissible use of multilogistic approximations for the parameter of the average number of contacts per person per day.

5. With small modifications of the multilogistic approximation, the model curve graphics were obtained nearly indistinguishable from the real graphs. This confirms the adequacy of the proposed model and the expediency of its practical use to optimize the management of epidemic control measures while maintaining acceptable economic growth both for Russia and for other countries of the world.

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